

Evaluating the Mechanical and Environmental Impacts of Eggshell Powder as a Partial Cement Replacement in Sustainable Concrete Production

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ABSTRACT:

This study investigates the feasibility of eggshell powder (ESP) as a partial replacement for ordinary Portland cement (OPC) in sustainable concrete production. Laboratory tests evaluated the mechanical and workability properties of ESP concrete at 0%, 4%, and 10% replacement levels. Results show that up to 10% ESP replacement improves compressive (53.52 MPa) and split-tensile (2.487 MPa) strengths, exceeding the control mix. However, workability decreases with higher ESP content. The study also shows that ESP reduces the carbon footprint by approximately 10% and contributes to waste recycling. The findings suggest ESP's potential as a sustainable material in eco-friendly construction, warranting further research on long-term durability, carbon sequestration, and economic feasibility.

Keywords: Eggshell powder, Sustainable concrete, Ordinary Portland cement, Mechanical properties, Workability, Carbon footprint reduction, Waste recycling.

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INTRODUCTION

The global construction industry's reliance on cement significantly contributes to environmental degradation, accounting for approximately 8% of global CO₂ emissions annually [2,7,9]. Cement production processes, including calcination and fuel combustion, emit around 900 kg of CO₂ for every ton produced [13,16]. This statistic highlights the urgent need for sustainable alternatives to traditional cement. Researchers have explored various waste materials as partial replacements for cement [19], with eggshell powder (ESP) emerging as a promising candidate due to its high calcium carbonate (CaCO₃) content, which is essential for cementitious properties [21,25]. ESP has been shown to possess potential applications not only in concrete but also in biodiesel production and the removal of ionic pollutants, further emphasizing its versatility [10].

Investigations into the use of ESP as a partial replacement for ordinary Portland cement (OPC) have yielded mixed results. Some studies suggest that ESP can replace up to 10% of cement, enhancing both compressive and tensile strength [4,11,24]. For instance, A study by [6] demonstrated that a combination of ESP and other materials could be effectively used in concrete mixes, yielding satisfactory results. Also, other studies report a reduction in strength beyond a 4% ESP replacement, indicating that the optimal percentage may vary [5,14,18]. The discrepancies in optimal ESP replacement percentages may be attributed to variations in the chemical composition of ESP, particularly its lower calcium oxide (CaO) content compared to OPC [17,20]. Furthermore, existing research has predominantly focused on the mechanical properties of ESP, often neglecting its environmental and economic implications [3,8].

This study aims to address the identified knowledge gap by investigating the optimal percentage of ESP replacement, evaluating both mechanical properties and sustainability aspects of ESP-concrete. Specifically, the research will examine the effects of 0%, 4%, and 10% ESP replacements on compressive and split-tensile strength over 1, 7, and 28 days, alongside an analysis of carbon footprint reduction and cost savings [12]. Employing standardized tests ensures comparability with existing literature, while the inclusion of carbon footprint analysis aligns with contemporary sustainability concerns, supporting the circular economy and mitigating the environmental impact of construction activities [23].

The findings of this study hold significant implications for both the construction industry and environmental sustainability efforts. By demonstrating the viability of ESP as a partial cement replacement, this research contributes to the growing body of work advocating for sustainable construction materials [15]. The reduction in cement usage not only decreases CO₂ emissions but also lowers construction costs, making ESP-concrete an economically viable option, particularly in regions with abundant eggshell waste [6]. The potential for ESP to serve as a sustainable alternative aligns with global efforts to reduce the carbon footprint of the construction industry while promoting the recycling of waste materials [22].

METHODS

The research was conducted using the methodology depicted in Figure 3.1 below, which compares the mechanical strength (compressive and split-tensile strength) of control concrete to that of partially replaced eggshell-cement concrete in order to obtain the optimal percentage of eggshell powder that can be used to replace cement in the production of concrete in order to yield an adequate concrete in terms of strength and workability as described in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Flowchart illustrating the Method used in the Research Work

Materials

The materials used in this study included ordinary Portland cement (OPC), fine aggregates, coarse aggregates, potable water, and eggshell powder (ESP). The OPC used was a local Type I cement with a strength grade of 52.5 N, complying with EN 197-1 standards. Fine aggregates with particle

sizes between 0.25 mm and 2 mm, and uncrushed coarse aggregates (10 mm and 20 mm) were used following BS EN 12620 standards. Potable water was used for both mixing and curing processes.

The eggshell powder (ESP) was collected from commercial sources and underwent a preparation process before use. The preparation involved:

1. Collection and Cleaning: Eggshells were collected, washed, and rinsed with clean potable water and laid-out as shown in fig.2.

Figure 2. Boiling of Eggshells to Remove Any Available Germs and Proteins

2. Drying: The cleaned eggshells were dried in an oven at 105°C for 24 hours to ensure proper dehydration.

Figure 3. A Well-Blended Concrete

3. Grinding: After drying, the eggshells were manually ground using a mortar and pestle to form a fine powder. The powder was then sieved to remove lumps and ensure homogeneity in the cement mixture.

(a) (b)
Figure 4. Moulding and Curing of Concrete Samples

Sample Preparation

The mix design was based on a concrete grade of 35MPa with a water-to-cement ratio of 0.52. Three concrete mixtures were prepared with ESP replacement levels of 0%, 4%, and 10% of the cement by weight. Each mixture was subjected to mechanical testing after curing for 1, 7, and 28 days.

Table 1. Quantities of Materials Used for the Preparation of Concrete Mixtures

% ESP Replacement	Cement (kg)	Water (kg)	Fine Aggregate (kg)	Coarse Aggregate (kg)
0%	115	53.33	225.47	435.47
4%	110.4	53.33	225.47	435.47
10%	80.5	53.33	225.47	435.47

Each mixture was batched in two stages due to the limited capacity of the mixing equipment. Fine and coarse aggregates were first mixed for 5 minutes, followed by the addition of OPC or ESP and a further 5 minutes of mixing. Water was added last, and the mixture was mixed for an additional 5 minutes to ensure homogeneity as shown in figure 3.

Testing Methods

1. Workability Tests

The workability of each mixture was evaluated using the slump test and vee bee test as per BS EN 12350-2 standards. The slump cone was filled in three layers, with each layer tamped 25 times. After filling, the cone was lifted vertically, and the reduction in height was measured to determine the slump. The vee bee test measured the time it took for the surface of the concrete to flatten under vibration as shown in fig.5.

2. Compressive Strength Tests

A total of 27 concrete cubes, each measuring 150 mm x 150 mm x 150 mm, were cast for compressive strength testing. Three samples from each ESP percentage (0%, 4%, 10%) were tested at 1, 7, and 28 days of curing. The cubes were cured in water at 20°C and tested using a compressive strength machine with a maximum capacity of 135 MPa. The set-up is shown in figure 6. The compressive strength was calculated by dividing the maximum load sustained by the cubes by their cross-sectional area.

(a)

(b)

Figure 5. The Slump and Vee Bee Test

Figure 6. Crushing the Concrete Cube

3. Split-Tensile Strength Tests

Nine cylindrical concrete samples (150 mm diameter and 300 mm length) were prepared to measure split-tensile strength. The samples were cured for 1, 7, and 28 days in a water tank at 20°C. The splitting tensile test was conducted using a tensile strength machine by applying a compressive force along the cylinder's diameter until the specimen failed. The set-up is shown in figure 7. The tensile strength was calculated using the formula:

$$\text{Tensile Strength} = \frac{2P}{\pi ld} \quad (1)$$

where P is the maximum load before failure, l is the length of the cylinder, and d is the diameter.

Figure 7. Split – Tensile Strength Test

4. Carbon Footprint Calculation

To estimate the potential carbon footprint reduction, the study used the widely accepted figure of 900 kg CO₂ per ton of cement produced [7]. The reduction in CO₂ emissions was calculated based on the percentage of cement replaced by ESP. For each ton of concrete produced with 10% ESP replacement, a CO₂ reduction of approximately 90 kg was achieved.

Experimental Setup

The experimental setup involved the following equipment:

Portable Mixer: Used to blend aggregates, cement, and ESP into a homogenous concrete mix.

Slump Test Cone and Vee Bee Test Apparatus: Used to assess the workability of each mixture.

Compressive Strength Machine: Used to crush concrete cubes and measure compressive strength, with a maximum capacity of 135 MPa.

Tensile Strength Machine: Used to perform split-tensile strength tests on cylindrical samples.

Curing Tanks: Maintained at a constant temperature of 20°C to cure the concrete samples.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The mechanical properties and environmental impact of concrete with varying percentages of eggshell powder (ESP) as a partial replacement for ordinary Portland cement (OPC) were analyzed. The computation of compressive strength, split-tensile strength, and workability parameters relied on established formulas commonly used in concrete engineering research.

Table 2 displays the characteristics of eggshell adopted in the laboratory work in comparison with the Ordinary Portland Cement.

Table 2. Physical and Chemical Properties of ESP and OPC

Property	Cement (OPC)	Eggshell Powder (ESP)
Colour	<i>Grey</i>	<i>Off – white</i>
Size (μm)	1– 30	1– 35
Specific Gravity	3.15	2.9
Calcium Oxide (CaO) %	62– 66	98.21
Silicon Dioxide (SiO_2) %	19– 23	0
Iron Oxide (Fe_2O_3) %	2– 4	0.08

The particle size distributions of ESP (1-35 μm) and OPC (1-30 μm) exhibit minimal differences, indicating compatibility with cementitious materials. The specific gravity of ESP (2.9) is slightly lower than OPC's (3.15), making ESP suitable for lightweight concrete applications. These minor differences suggest that ESP can be used as a viable partial substitute for OPC in concrete production.

The chemical composition of ESP reveals high calcium oxide (CaO) content (98.21%), advantageous for strength development, exceeding OPC's CaO content (62-66%). However, ESP lacks silicon dioxide (SiO_2), essential for forming calcium silicate hydrates (C-S-H), which may require mix design modifications.

The results presented in Table 3 and the corresponding plot in figure 8 provides a clear indication of how the compressive strength of concrete changes with the incorporation of eggshell powder (ESP) as a partial replacement for ordinary Portland cement (OPC) at varying curing periods (1, 7, and 28 days). Concrete mixes containing 0%, 4%, and 10% ESP were evaluated, and the trends observed suggest that the addition of ESP positively influences compressive strength development, particularly at the later stages of curing.

The results show a significant increase in compressive strength with ESP replacement, particularly at 28 days.

Table 3. Compressive Strength of Concrete with ESP (MPa)

Curing Days	0% ESP	4% ESP	10% ESP
1 Day	32.81	33.41	34.94
7 Days	43.28	44.31	45.85
28 Days	47.59	50.04	53.52

Figure 8. Compressive Strength of Concrete with ESP

The significant increase in compressive strength with ESP replacement suggests that ESP can be used as a sustainable partial replacement for ordinary Portland cement (OPC). This finding supports previous studies that have shown the potential of ESP as a supplementary cementitious material. However, the lower silicon dioxide (SiO₂) content in ESP may require mix design modifications for higher replacement levels.

The findings indicate that using ESP as a partial cement substitute—up to 10%—is a viable strategy for producing high-strength, sustainable concrete. This offers an eco-friendly alternative to OPC that can reduce the environmental impact of cement production while maintaining structural integrity.

The split-tensile strength results for concrete with varying percentages of eggshell powder (ESP) as a partial replacement for ordinary Portland cement (OPC) are presented in Table 4.

Table 4. Split-Tensile Strength of Concrete with ESP (MPa)

Curing Days	0% ESP	4% ESP	10% ESP
1 Day	1.863	1.895	1.903
7 Days	1.932	1.965	2.015
28 Days	2.14	2.217	2.487

The corresponding plot in figure 9 illustrates the trend of split-tensile strength development with ESP replacement.

The results show a consistent improvement in split-tensile strength with increasing ESP content. At 1 day, the control concrete mix (0% ESP) exhibits a split-tensile strength of 1.863 MPa, while the 4% and 10% ESP mixes display slightly higher strengths. By 7 days, the split-tensile strength continues to rise, with the 10% ESP mix recording the highest value. At 28 days, the 10% ESP mix achieves a split-tensile strength of 2.487 MPa, representing a 16% increase over the control sample.

The observed improvement in split-tensile strength with ESP replacement can be attributed to the high calcium oxide (CaO) content in ESP. The CaO content promotes early and continued hydration, leading to the formation of additional calcium silicate hydrates (C-S-H) that strengthen interfacial transition zones.

The refined microstructure resulting from ESP replacement contributes to enhanced tensile properties. The findings suggest that ESP can serve as a viable partial replacement for OPC, particularly in applications where tensile strength is critical.

The environmental benefits of using ESP as a sustainable material in concrete production are significant, aligning with the study's objectives.

Figure 9. Split-Tensile Strength of Concrete with ESP Replacement

The use of ESP as a partial cement substitute (up to 10%) offers dual benefits: reduced carbon footprint associated with cement production and enhanced mechanical properties of concrete. This supports the broader goal of reducing cement use in construction while maintaining structural integrity.

The workability of concrete mixes containing varying percentages of eggshell powder (ESP) as a partial replacement for ordinary Portland cement (OPC) is summarized in Table 5 and the corresponding plot in fig.10. Workability was evaluated through two key tests: the slump test and the vee bee time test, which measure the consistency and fluidity of fresh concrete.

Table 5. Workability of Concrete with ESP Replacement

ESP Percentage	Slump Value (mm)	Vee Bee Time (s)
0%	30	6.64
4%	15	13.48
10%	12.5	15.28

The incorporation of eggshell powder (ESP) into concrete mixes reduces workability as the percentage of ESP increases. Slump test results show a decrease in slump value from 30 mm (control) to 12.5 mm (10% ESP), indicating significant reduction in workability. Vee bee time results exhibit an inverse relationship, increasing from 6.64 seconds (control) to 15.28 seconds (10% ESP), further indicating reduced workability.

The reduction in workability is attributed to ESP's fineness, particle size distribution, and specific gravity. ESP's slightly coarser particle size range and lower specific gravity compared to ordinary Portland cement (OPC) may lead to increased water demand and reduced mix cohesion. However, concrete workability can be adjusted by incorporating admixtures or modifying the water-to-cement ratio.

Despite reduced workability, ESP's environmental benefits and contribution to enhanced strength make it a promising option for sustainable concrete production. Adjustments may be necessary to optimize workability for specific construction requirements. The study's findings support exploring ESP as a sustainable alternative to OPC, considering mix design modifications to manage workability issues. With proper adjustments, ESP can remain a viable option for sustainable concrete.

Figure 10. Slump Values and Vee Bee Times for ESP Concrete

CONCLUSION

The results of this study, shows that eggshell powder (ESP) exhibit similar physical and chemical properties to those of ordinary Portland cement (OPC), making it a suitable partial replacement for OPC in sustainable concrete production. The presence of high calcium oxide (CaO) content in ESP contributes to improved compressive and tensile strengths, particularly at replacement levels up to 10%. The maximum compressive strength of 53.52 MPa and split-tensile strength of 2.487 MPa were achieved at 10% ESP after 28 days of curing, which exceeded the strength of the control mix.

The results also indicate that as the percentage of ESP increases, the workability of the concrete decreases, as evidenced by lower slump values and longer Vee Bee times. This reduction in workability is attributed to the faster hydration process facilitated by ESP, which accelerates the formation of calcium hydrates. Nevertheless, the decrease in workability can be mitigated through the use of appropriate admixtures or adjustments to the water-cement ratio.

Critical Conclusion

This research establishes that up to 10% replacement of OPC with ESP can enhance the mechanical properties of concrete while reducing the carbon footprint associated with cement production. The high calcium content in ESP contributes positively to concrete strength, making it a viable and sustainable alternative to conventional cement. Furthermore, the results align with other studies that suggest that ESP can be effectively used in concrete production to reduce environmental impact and promote waste recycling.

Implications

The implications of this research are significant for the construction industry. Using ESP as a partial replacement for cement can lead to the production of more environmentally friendly concrete, reducing the carbon emissions associated with cement production by up to 10%. Additionally, ESP offers a cost-effective alternative to OPC, potentially lowering overall construction costs while maintaining the structural integrity of concrete. Moreover, the use of ESP contributes to waste recycling, addressing environmental concerns related to the disposal of eggshells in landfills.

Future research should focus on:

1. Durability testing: Investigating the long-term durability of ESP concrete, including tests for water absorption, modulus of elasticity, and permeability, to assess its performance under different environmental conditions.
2. Carbon sequestration potential: Assessing the ability of ESP-reinforced concrete to absorb CO₂ during the carbonation process, thus further reducing the overall carbon footprint.
3. Economic feasibility: Conducting a cost-benefit analysis for the large-scale application of ESP in concrete production, taking into account sourcing, processing, and transportation costs relative to conventional concrete production.

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